

Ab initio and DFT study of the electronic state, geometry and harmonic frequencies of OBBO.....HX (X = F, Cl, Br) intermolecular complexes

Mudassir M. Husain^a, Vibha Saxena^b and H. C. Tandon^{b*}

^aPhysics Section, Department of Applied Sciences and Humanities, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Jamia Millia Islamia (a Central University), New Delhi-110 025, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Sri Venkateswara College (University of Delhi), New Delhi-110 021, India

E-mail : hctwave@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 8 June 2009, revised 1 February 2010, accepted 8 February 2010

Abstract : The present work, investigates theoretically the existence of linear H-bonding formed between diboron oxide (as proton acceptor) and hydrogen halides (as proton donor) in their ground state. *Ab initio* and DFT/HF/FLYP methods using 6-311G** basis set under C_{∞v} point group symmetry have been utilized to obtain optimized geometries, electronic parameters and harmonic frequencies. The dipole moment (μ) of halides show a decrease in the values after H-bond complex formation. The binding and dissociation energies show a decreasing order OBBO.....HF > OBBO.....HCl > OBBO.....HBr. The static polarizabilities (α) of complex are also discussed.

Keywords : Boron oxide, DFT, red-shift, polarizabilities, dipole moment, geometry.

Introduction

It has been known for sometime¹ that the gaseous species B₂O₂ is generated when a mixture of boron and B₂O₃ is heated to ~ 1200 °C. At that time, the molecular structure of B₂O₂ was assumed to be linear, symmetric O=B-B=O isoelectronic with cyanogens. Subsequently, an alternate structure B-O-B-O was proposed² based on bond energy considerations. The topologies of these structures were examined by *ab initio* calculations at the STO-3G level and by semiempirical (MNDO) methods³. Both calculations showed O=B-B=O to be more stable. Further support to this structure was obtained from infrared spectroscopy of the matrix isolated species. As we know, B₂O₂ is isoelectronic with N≡C-C≡N, and recently Varadwaj and Husain⁴ investigated theoretically the existence of linear H-bonding between C-cyanophosphoryne (as proton acceptor) and hydrogen halides (as proton donor) in their ground states. In view of this, we have investigated of linear H-bonding between OBBO (as proton acceptor) and HX (as proton donor), in which the charge is donated by O-atom of B₂O₂ into the σ -orbital of the acids (HX).

Although, B₂O₂ has zero dipole moment, but due to

the presence of lone pairs on O-atoms, it is capable of interacting with other species, through intermolecular interaction. Numerous attempts have been made experimentally as well as theoretically to understand short lived H-bonded complexes⁵⁻⁸. Recently, some more work on H-bond complexes, namely NH.....XC blue-shifting H-bond in monohalomethanes with HNO⁹, CH.....OH bond¹⁰, open-shell complexes pairing H₂X with HXX (X = S, O)¹¹, CH₄.....H₂O H-bond complexes¹², have been reported. To the best of our knowledge, no study, either theoretical or experimental has been carried out so far, for the OBBO.....HX (X = F, Cl, Br) complexes.

Computational details :

The quantum mechanical calculations using *ab initio* and Density Functional Theory (DFT) with Hartree-Fock exchange potential and LYP (Lee, Yang and Parr)¹³ as correlation functional have been performed for hydrogen halide, B₂O₂ and their complexes. The polarized basis sets 6-311G** and 6-31G** have been employed for hydrogen halides and B₂O₂ respectively. The molecular geometries of the monomers and their complexes, were, first, optimized at AM1 (semiempirical) level and then re-optimized at *ab initio* and LYP level keeping root mean

square limit (rms) gradient as 0.01 kcal/Å mol and using Polak-Ribierre gradient method; an algorithm which is fast and accurate, has been employed at all levels of calculations. The electronic and energy parameters have been computed to establish the potential energy surfaces of the above systems. The harmonic vibrational frequencies have also been calculated for the monomers and their complexes for further understanding of H-bonding in the form of frequency shift in the complexes. All calculations have been carried out using Hyperchem 7.5 program¹⁴. In addition, the dipole polarizability values have also been computed at three different fields 0.005, 0.05 and 0.5 a.u.'s as it is well known that the dipole moment and polarizability parameters are the two important entities which signify the non-linear optical properties. Whenever, there is some dipole interaction during the complex formation, these properties assume paramount importance. Furthermore, we tried B3LYP exchange and correlation functionals for equilibrium geometry calculations of the system, but the bond lengths of the monomers were found to be very large in comparison to experimental values. Hence, LYP functional, quite precise and accurate has been used here.

Results and discussion

The computed values are given in Tables 1-5. The equilibrium geometries (ground state) of monomers and their complexes, calculated both at unrestricted Hartree-

Fock and DFT levels are displayed in Table 1. It can be seen that the computed vertical parameters are in close agreement with the available experimental values for HX monomers. The bond lengths of B₂O₂ are consistent with the available high level theoretical results. The HX bond length shows an increase with respect to its monomer, during the H-bond complex formation alongwith the O-B of B₂O₂ (where H is bonded to O-atom). These changes in bond length of monomers predict the H-bonded formation. One interesting point regarding the HBr complexation with B₂O₂ is that the H-bond formation is not linear unlike HF and HCl, but angular. The angles of HOB and O...HBr are found to be 148° and 169° at UHF level. It may be attributed to large atomic size of Br-atom which could not hold the electronic charge at its centre but seemed to be delocalized. This phenomenon needs more attention and explanation at theoretical and experimental levels. The stabilization energies of monomers and their complexes alongwith H-bond energies are reported in Table 2. The computed H-bond energies are in the order HF > HCl > HBr at both levels of theoretical methods. DFT gives slightly larger values than *ab initio* which is quite understandable in the context of different methodologies of these procedures. The dipole moments and HOMO-LUMO energy gap also show the similar trend of decreasing values as we go from HF to HBr complexation. Moreover, the ionization energy level raised in HF by 2.2117 eV during H-bond complexation in comparison to

Table 1. Geometrical parameters of HX (HF, HCl, HBr), B₂O₂ and their complexes computed by *ab initio* [using 6-311G** basis set for HX and 6-31G** for B₂O₂ and complexes] and DFT [using HF-LYP] calculations

System	Bond length (Å)		Bond angle (°)		Bond length (Å) Experimental ^b
	<i>ab initio</i>	DFT	<i>ab initio</i>	DFT	
HF	0.8960	0.9154			0.9168
HCl	1.2702	1.3043			1.2746
HBr	1.4093	1.4481			1.4144
B ₂ O ₂					
O=B	1.1819	1.6683/1.668 ^a			
B-B	1.6663	1.1723/1.182 ^a			
HF...OBBO (H-bonded)					
H-F	0.9017	0.9222			
O=B (<i>r</i> ₁)	1.1838	1.1791			
B-B (<i>r</i> ₂)	1.6683	1.6674			

Table-1 (contd.)

O=B (r_3)	1.1805	1.1763		
H...O	1.8901	1.8826		
HCl...B ₂ O ₂ (H-bonded)				
H-Cl	1.2746	1.3209		
O=B	1.1836	1.1773		
B-B	1.6678	1.6628		
O=B	1.1808	1.1729		
H...O	2.1576	2.1371		
HBr...OBBO				
H-Br	1.4121	1.4587		
O=B	1.1840	1.1752		
B-B	1.6680	1.6646		
O=B	1.1809	1.1728		
H...O	2.2843	2.2677		
∠ H...O-B			148.0	149.0
∠ Br-H...O			169.0	168.0

^aRef. 2 ; ^bRefs. 15, 16.

Table 2. Energetics of HF, HCl, HBr, B₂O₂ and their complexes

Systems	B.E (-E)		μ		HOMO		LUMO		$\Delta\epsilon$	
	(kcal/mol)		(debye)		(eV)		(eV)		(eV)	
	<i>ab initio</i>	DFT	<i>ab initio</i>	DFT	<i>ab initio</i>	DFT	<i>ab initio</i>	DFT	<i>ab initio</i>	DFT
HF	62780.38	63007.95	1.980	2.045	-17.3957	-18.3246	4.0992	3.2452	21.4949	21.5698
HCl	288713.95	289169.19	1.826 ^a	1.522	-13.0121	-13.8276	3.3292	2.4636	16.3413	16.2912
			1.094 ^a							
HBr	1614554.12	1615635.50	1.145	1.202	-11.8048	-12.6080	3.0181	2.0792	14.8229	14.6872
			0.827 ^a							
B ₂ O ₂	124989.63	125554.19	0.0	0.0	-14.6313	-15.6495	1.6899	0.9382	16.3212	16.5877
HF...B ₂ O ₂	187777.14	188570.47	2.886	2.980	-15.184	-16.1771	1.1376	0.3029	16.3216	16.4800
			1.740 ^b							
HCl...B ₂ O ₂	413708.28	414728.50	2.295	2.148	-12.4789	-13.2833	1.2797	0.4641	13.7586	13.7474
			1.520 ^b							
HBr...B ₂ O ₂	1739547.40	1741193.88	1.864	1.941	-11.4269	-12.2280	1.3413	0.5451	12.7682	12.7731
			1.460 ^b							
H^{bond}										
(HF-B ₂ O ₂)	7.13 [8.33]									
(HCl-B ₂ O ₂)	4.70 [5.12]									
(HBr-B ₂ O ₂)	3.65 [4.19]									

^aRef. 15; ^bRef. 4 the values are of PCCN...HX complex for the comparison of trend in HX complex. Numbers in square bracket are DFT results.

0.5332 eV and 0.3779 eV for HCl and HBr respectively (see Table-2). This, also indicates strong H-bonding in HF...B₂O₂ complex. The harmonic vibrational frequencies of halides, B₂O₂ and their complexes are reported in

Table 2. The HX monomers, being diatomic molecule show only one mode of vibration and B₂O₂ predicted to show five modes of vibrations, out of which three are of σ -type and other two are π -type. Theoretically it should

Table 3. Selected vibrational frequency (cm^{-1}) and intensity (km/mol) for free HX and their complexes with B_2O_2 obtained at *ab initio* level

System	Mode	Frequency	
		HF	Expt.
HF	Symm. stretch	4513 (15.7)	4138. ^{3a}
HCl	Symm. stretch	3144 (50)	2991
HBr	Symm. stretch	2796 (11)	2649
B_2O_2			
B=O/B=O	Symm. stretch	2328 (0.0)	2060
B=O/B=O	Asymm. stretch	2141 (354)	1897.8
B-B	Symm. stretch	633 (0)	585
B_2O_2 -HF			
HF	Symm. stretch	4380 (741)	-
B_2O_2	Symm. stretch	2338 (0.7)	-
B_2O_2	Asymm. stretch	2158 (424)	-
B-B	Symm. stretch	638 (1.5)	-
F-H... B_2O_2	Symm. stretch	149 (3)	-
B_2O_2 -HCl			
HCl	Symm. stretch	3097 (165)	-
B_2O_2	Asymm. stretch	2135 (395)	-
B-B	Symm. stretch	634 (0.3)	-
Cl-H... B_2O_2	Symm. stretch	81 (0.7)	-
B_2O_2 -OBr			
H-Br	Symm. stretch	2763 (132)	-
B_2O_2	Symm. stretch	2326 (0.4)	-
B_2O_2	Asymm. stretch	2132 (417)	-
B-B	Symm. stretch	632 (0.7)	-
Br-H... B_2O_2	Symm. stretch	63 (0.6)	-

^aTaken from Ref. 17.

Table 4. *Ab initio* level computed harmonic frequencies (cm^{-1}) of $\text{OBBO}\cdots\text{HX}$ (X = F, Cl, Br) complexes

H-X (stretch)	4380	3097	2763
	(4513) $^1\text{S}_1$	(3144) $^1\text{S}_1$	(2796) $^1\text{S}_1$
O=B (stretch)	2338	2330	2326
	(2141)	(2141)	(2141)
B-B (stretch)	638	634	632
	(633)	(633)	(633)
O...H (stretch)	149	81	63
O...H-X (bend in-plane)	506	460	277
O...H-X (bend out-of-plane)	496	380	263

The numbers in parentheses are the vibrational frequencies of monomers.

have seen absorption peaks (3N-5) but two bending modes (out-of-plane and in-plane) are degenerate. The calculated vibrational numbers of B_2O_2 (scaled) are in good

agreement with the experimental values. It shows that the high level quantum chemical methods reproduce the experimental results quite successfully. The approximate descriptions of the intramolecular normal modes follow those of the corresponding monomer vibrations, while the intermolecular normal modes are described as O...B stretching and liberation of HX (X = F, Cl, Br) and B_2O_2 monomer units, either in-plane or out-of-plane (Table 3). It is obvious from these results that HX stretch show red-shift by 133, 47 and 33 cm^{-1} respectively. The O...B stretch (H-bond involved) show an increase in the frequency shifts (blue-shift) from HF to HBr respectively. This is in tune with the fact that during any bond formation between two molecules there is a shift in frequency.

The concise comparison of the vibrational frequencies of the complexes are given in Table 4. As we pointed out in the text that dipole polarizabilities alongwith dipole moment values are two important factors, which can explain and justify the chemical behaviour of these molecules, in free and bonded state. Hence, we calculated the dipole polarizability values of these systems at three different fields 0.005, 0.05 and 0.5 atomic units. The computed values are shown in Table 5. The mean polarizability (α_m) values and tensors (α_{xx} , α_{yy} , α_{zz}) further confirms the H-bond complexation between HX and B_2O_2 . These results are plotted for the clarity of the trend follows and shown in Fig. 1.

Conclusion :

The H-bond complex formation of molecular species can be studied quite successfully by using high level theoretical methods, choosing standard basis sets. The binding energies, dipole moments, and HOMO-LUMO energy gaps are computed and are found to be in close agreement with the available experimental and theoretical results. The stability of the H-bonded complex is in the order of HF > HCl > HBr. This study is further confirmed by the vibrational frequency shift during the intermolecular bond formation. The non-linear optical properties can also be used quite successfully to assess the complex formation.

Table 5. Dipole polarizabilities and tensors of HX, B₂O₂ and their complexes at different fields

Systems	Static electric field (a.u) [applied along axial position]														
	0.005				0.05				0.5						
	α_m	α_{xx}	α_{yy}	α_{zz}	$\Delta\alpha_m$	α_m	α_{xx}	α_{yy}	α_{zz}	$\Delta\alpha_m$	α_m	α_{xx}	α_{yy}	α_{zz}	$\Delta\alpha_m$
HF	2.53	4.16	1.72	1.72		2.54	4.20	1.72	1.72		3.39	6.47	1.85	1.85	
HCl	8.71	12.84	6.65	6.65		8.81	13.06	6.69	6.69		12.05	17.56	9.29	9.29	
HBr	13.44	18.24	11.04	11.04		13.61	18.61	11.11	11.11		15.88	21.90	12.88	12.88	
B ₂ O ₂	20.54	14.43	32.75	14.43		20.85	14.49	33.55	14.49		32.19	18.06	60.46	18.06	
HF...B ₂ O ₂	23.84	17.14	33.26	21.13	0.77	24.17	17.21	33.99	21.29	0.78	61.99	27.92	110.37	47.70	26.41
HCl...B ₂ O ₂	30.66	22.09	44.17	25.77	1.41	31.65	29.38	43.57	22.00	1.99	93.50	36.08	179.71	64.72	49.26
HBr...B ₂ O ₂	36.23	27.36	48.85	32.48	2.25	37.13	27.58	50.51	32.99	2.67	105.72	46.83	18.76	89.58	57.65

α_m : mean polarizability; α_{xx} , α_{yy} , α_{zz} : tensor components; $\Delta\alpha_m = \alpha_m(\text{HX}\cdots\text{B}_2\text{O}_2) - \alpha_m(\text{HX} + \text{B}_2\text{O}_2)$.

Fig. 1. Variation of polarization of molecules and their complexes in static electric field (applied along axial position).

Acknowledgement

The authors are highly grateful to the Referee for valuable comments and suggestions.

References

- M. G. Inghram, R. F. Porter and W. A. Chupka, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, **25**, 498.
- B. M. Ruccik, L. A. Curtiss and J. Berkowitz, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1984, **80**, 3962.
- R. L. DeKock and M. R. Barbachyn, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 2645.
- P. R. Varadwaj and M. M. Husain, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2006, **424**, 227.
- D. J. Millen, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1978, **1**, 45.
- B. O. Wang, Z. R. Li, D. Wu, X. Y. Hao, R. J. Li and C. C. Sun, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2003, **91**, 375.
- A. C. Legon, D. D. Lister and C. A. Rego, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1992, **189**, 221.
- A. C. Legon and J. M. A. Thumwood, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2000, **113**, 5278.
- M. Solimonnejad and S. Scheiner, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2007, **III**, 4431.
- S. Scheiner and T. Kar, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2008, **112**, 11854.
- M. Solimonnejad and S. Scheiner, *Mol. Phys.*, 2009, **107**, 713.
- B. Raghvendra and E. Arunan, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2008, **467**, 37.
- B. G. Johnson, P. M. Gill and J. A. Pople, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1993, **98**, 5612.
- HYPERCHEM 7.5 program, Hypercube Inc., Florida, 2003.
- K. Huber and G. Herzberg, "Molecular Spectra and Molecular Structure IV. Constants of Diatomic Molecules", Van Nostrand-Reinhold, New York, 1979.
- R. N. Sileo and T. A. Cool, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1976, **65**, 117.
- L. B. Kier and L. H. Hall, "Molecular Connectivity in Structure Activity Analysis", Research Studies Press, Letchworth, 1986, pp. 20-25.